

2D Gaussian Splatting for Geometrically Accurate 3D Object Reconstruction

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I declare that the work presented in this report is entirely my own, except where otherwise stated and acknowledged. This report has not been submitted, in whole or in part, for any other academic qualification or degree at any other academic institution.

Abstract

Gaussian Splatting approaches have proven to be a very effective method of 3D scene reconstruction and rendering. However, general pipelines of Gaussian Splatting approaches reconstruct entire scene which might not be desirable if the goal is the reconstruction of only specific object present in the scene. This makes the entire reconstruction pipeline computationally expensive and inefficient for target object-specific reconstruction task. We propose utilizing the masks of the object in order to achieve efficient object-centric reconstruction. The model can produce geometrically accurate object-centric reconstruction with significantly faster training time (67% faster).

Keywords : Gaussian Splatting, Novel View Synthesis, Surface Reconstruction, Radiance Fields, 2D/3D Gaussians

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1 Introduction

The 3D reconstruction of an object from multi-view 2D images is widely studied topic in field of computer vision and graphics. The traditional photogrammetry methods like Structure-from-motion (SfM) and Multi-view-stereo (MVS) rely on modular framework like feature extraction, feature matching, depth prediction and fusion. Recently, 3D Gaussian Splatting 3DGS (Kerbl et al., 2023) has gained significant attention in 3D reconstruction and novel view synthesis (NVS) due to its explicit nature and ability to deliver faster real-time NVS at high resolution. Although the 3DGS is rapidly developing and has been adopted in multiple domains, it lacks in accurately representing the geometry of an object. This is due to conflicting nature of the volumetric radiance representation of 3D Gaussians with thin surfaces.

A more effective way of representing the intricate geometry would be representing with surfels (surface elements) as shown by other works (Pfister et al., 2000; Zwicker et al., 2001a; Zwicker et al., 2001b). Surfels are widely used in SLAM and other robotic tasks but the drawbacks is that the ground truth geometry, depth sensor data are required or they operate under constrained scenarios in known lighting.

2D Gaussian Splatting 2DGS for 3D reconstruction and NVS combines the benefits of both approaches while overcoming their limitations. In 2DGS the 3D scenes are represented by 2D primitives, each defining oriented elliptical disk, enabling it to capture the object geometry more accurately during rendering. In contrast to 3DGS which evaluates gaussian value at the intersection between ray and 3D gaussian, 2DGS utilizes explicit ray-splat intersection so that the perspective accuracy splatting is achieved (Huang et al., 2024) as illustrated in Figure 1. In addition 2DGS also introduces two regularization terms : depth distortion and normal consistency for better reconstruction and smooth surfaces as optimizing only with photometric loss yields noisy results(Huang et al., 2024).

Figure 1: Comparison of 2DGS and 3DGS. 3DGS utilizes different intersection planes for value evaluation when viewing from different viewpoints, resulting in inconsistency. 2DGS provides multi-view consistent value evaluations. (Huang et al., 2024)

Both the 3DGS and 2DGS methods reconstruct an entire scene which may not be ideal for the object focused reconstruction task. It is possible to extract meshes from both these approaches. However, creating a mesh of the specific object from a Gaussian representation of an entire scene is challenging. Since the object specific tasks only require the mesh of a specific object, training on the entire scene is inefficient and consumes unnecessary computing resource. Building upon

the already existing 2DGS framework, we plan to introduce the segmentation mask during the optimization process as mask loss to remove background Gaussians. This will achieve the object specific reconstruction task efficiently and faster.

2 Related Works

2.1 3D Gaussian Splatting (3DGS)

3D Gaussian Splatting (3DGS) (Kerbl et al., 2023) utilizes 3D Gaussians primitives to model the geometry and render images using differentiable volume rendering. The 3D Gaussians are defined by 3D covariance matrix Σ defined in world space centered at a point (mean) μ as :

$$G(x) = e^{-\frac{1}{2}(x)^T \Sigma^{-1}(x)} \quad (1)$$

Each Gaussian along with the position (center, μ) and covariance (Σ) are also characterized by its opacity (α) and spherical harmonic (c) which represents view-independent color. For rendering, the 3D Gaussians needs to be transformed into 2D image spaces. Given a viewing transformation W the covariance matrix (Σ') in camera coordinates is as follows :

$$\Sigma' = JW\Sigma W^T J^T \quad (2)$$

where J is Jacobian of affine approximation of projective transformation. For regularizing optimization covariance matrix is further decomposed into scaling matrix S and rotation matrix R :

$$\Sigma = RSS^T R^T \quad (3)$$

Each of the above mentioned parameters characterizing the Gaussians are learnable and optimized via backpropagation.

2.2 2D Gaussian Splatting (2DGS)

2DGS (Huang et al., 2024) proposed use of the 2D primitives, flat planar disks, embedded in 3D space for modeling. With 2D Gaussian modeling, the primitive distributes densities within a planar disk, defining the normal as the direction of the steepest change of density. Each disk is characterized by (as illustrated in Figure 2) its central point p_k , two principal tangential vectors t_u and t_v , and scaling vector $S = (s_u, s_v)$ which controls the variance of 2D Gaussians. The primitive normal t_k is defined by two orthogonal tangential vectors; $t_w = t_u \times t_v$. The orientation can be then arranged as 3×3 rotation matrix $R = [t_u, t_v, t_w]$ and scaling factor into 3×3 diagonal matrix S with last entry zero. Therefore a 2D Gaussian is defined in a local tangent plane in world space, which is parameterized :

$$P(u, v) = p_k + s_u t_u u + s_v t_v v = H(u, v, 1, 1)^T \quad (4)$$

Figure 2: Illustration of 2D Gaussian Splatting. 2D Gaussian Splats are elliptical disks characterized by a center point p_k , tangential vectors t_u and t_v , and two scaling factors (s_u and s_v) control the variance.

$$H = \begin{bmatrix} s_u t_u & s_v t_v & 0 & p_k \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} RS & p_k \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

where $H \in 4 \times 4$ is a homogeneous transformation matrix representing the geometry of 2D Gaussian. For the point $\mathbf{u} = (u, v)$ in the uv space, its 2D Gaussian value can be then evaluated by standard Gaussian

$$G(u) = \exp\left(-\frac{u^2 + v^2}{2}\right) \quad (6)$$

The elliptical projection of the 2D Gaussian splats are sampled through the ray-splat intersection and accumulated via alpha-blending in image space (Huang et al., 2024).

The center p_k , scaling (s_u, s_v) and rotation (t_u, t_v) are learnable parameters that are optimized during the optimization process. Moreover, each 2D Gaussian has opacity α and view dependent color c parameterized in terms of spherical harmonics which are also optimized during optimization process.

3 Method

3.1 Object Reconstruction

Our method utilizes the 2DGS as baseline to achieve the goal of the efficient and geometrically accurate object reconstruction from a scene given the mask of the object M_i for the scene. This method introduces the mask loss using segmentation mask M_i and efficiently reconstruct target object from the scene while largely reducing the optimization time. An overview of method is shown in Figure 3 with the change highlighted. The section 3.2 will talk in details about the different loss terms used for optimization of our method.

3.2 Optimization

The goal is to reconstruct geometrically accurate 3D representation of an object given that we have set of the unstructured images I_i . During the pre-processing step, the SfM (Structure from motion) pipeline is utilized to obtain the camera pose P_i for each image in the set I_i . Additionally, SfM also

Figure 3: Overall workflow of the method with changes to the 2DGS pipeline highlighted

generates sparse point clouds as an output. 2DGS pipeline takes these sparse point clouds and use it as the basis for initialization of the Gaussian primitives. The optimization loop then starts, one of the input image I_i is selected and for its camera pose P_i a respective view R_i of 2D Gaussian representation is rendered. A photometric loss is then computed between the ground truth I_i and rendered view R_i . In addition to the photometric loss, 2DGS utilizes two regularization term ; depth distortion and normal consistency as loss during the optimization. An additional loss term is introduced, referred as mask loss, utilizing the segmentation mask M_i to efficiently reconstruct only the object of interest from the scene as explained in section 3.2.4 .

The proposed mask loss, however, conflicts with the 3DGS photometric loss, which encourages the Gaussians to match the colors of R_i and I_i even in regions where $M_i = 0$. Thus, the input images are masked to ensure the unnecessary portions of the scenes are not trained. Through backpropagation the position, shape, opacity and color are optimized to fit the appearance of I_i . Moreover, there is adaptive densification process that adaptively control the number of Gaussians and their density over unit volume allowing to go from the initial sparse set of Gaussians to a dense set for better representation of the scene (Kerbl et al., 2023). Densification begins at 600 iterations, occurs every 100 iterations, and stops before iteration 15000. During densification Gaussians with opacity α below a threshold ϵ_α , essentially transparent Gaussians, are removed. The adaptive densification process also takes into consideration of the under-reconstructed areas (missing geometric features) and over-reconstructed areas (Gaussians covering large areas) in the scene. For the under-constructed areas the Gaussians are cloned to fill in the geometry and for over-constructed areas the Gaussians are split into smaller Gaussians (Figure 4).

3.2.1 Photometric Loss

The photometric loss combines the L_1 loss and D-SSIM losses from 3DGS(ref).

$$\mathcal{L}_1 = \|R_i - I_i\|_1, \quad \mathcal{L}_{D-SSIM} = 1 - SSIM(R_i, I_i) \quad (7)$$

where R_i is rendering and I_i is corresponding ground truth image. Then the photometric loss function is :

$$\mathcal{L}_c = (1 - \lambda)\mathcal{L}_1 + \lambda\mathcal{L}_{D-SSIM} \quad (8)$$

Figure 4: Adaptive Gaussian densification scheme. Top row (under-reconstruction): When small-scale geometry (black outline) is insufficiently covered, the respective Gaussian is cloned. Bottom row (over-reconstruction): If small-scale geometry is represented by one large splat, it is split in two.

where $\lambda = 0.2$.

3.2.2 Depth Distortion

Depth distortion is one of the two regularization term introduced in 2DGS so that the model can capture geometry more accurately. The 3DGS doesn't consider the distance between the intersected Gaussian primitives which may lead to spread out Gaussians resulting in similar color and depth. While in case of surface rendering the ray is expected to intersect the first visible surface exactly once. So in 2DGS depth distortion loss was proposed minimizing the distance between ray splat intersection to concentrate the weight distribution along the rays :

$$\mathcal{L}_d = \sum_{i,j} w_i w_j |z_i - z_j| \quad (9)$$

where w_i is the blending weight of i-th intersection and z_i is the depth of intersection points (Huang et al., 2024).

3.2.3 Normal Consistency

It is another regularization term introduced in 2DGS which ensures the alignment of the 2D primitives with the actual surfaces. The normal of the splats are aligned with the gradient of the depth map as :

$$\mathcal{L}_n = \sum_i w_i (1 - n_i^T N) \quad (10)$$

where w_i is the blending weight of i-th intersection, n_i is the splat's normal and N is the normal estimated by gradient of the depth map (Huang et al., 2024).

3.2.4 Mask Loss

2DGS is able to produce the high-quality meshes of the scene and given few post-processing it is possible to get the mesh of an individual object. However, this would mean significant computational resource as well as time is wasted to reconstruct parts of the scene which would be discarded later. We aim to include the mask of an object during optimization loop such that only the necessary parts are reconstructed.

Given that I_i be the images and M_i being corresponding masks, with all pixels value in M_i equals 1 where the object is present and 0 otherwise, the aim is to render the view R_i which results in no Gaussians for background (where $M_i = 0$). We utilize a binary cross entropy loss as a mask loss (Yang et al., 2024) :

$$\mathcal{L}_m = -(m \log A + (1 - m) \log(1 - A)) \quad (11)$$

where m is the mask of object and A is the accumulated alphas from Gaussians during rendering R . It ensures that the opacity of background Gaussians is pushed towards transparency. The transparent Gaussians are then pruned out via threshold automatically as part of the density control from 3DGS.

3.2.5 Total Loss

The overall loss combines all of the loss term as :

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_c + \alpha \mathcal{L}_d + \beta \mathcal{L}_n + \delta \mathcal{L}_m \quad (12)$$

where α, β and δ controls the magnitude of the loss terms.

4 Experimentation

This section describes the experimental setup used for the object reconstruction task. The section 4.1 details about the datasets utilized for the optimization and evaluation, section 4.2 outlines the implementation details and section 4.3 presents the evaluation of the study.

4.1 Datasets

The datasets used for this study is a public dataset T-LESS (Hodan et al., 2017). The datasets includes training and test images captured from three synchronized sensors; i.e. a structured light RGB-D sensor Primesense Carmine 1.09, a time-of-flight RGB-D sensor Microsoft Kinect v2, and an RGB camera Canon IXUS 950 IS. Since the original purpose of the dataset is estimating 6D position of an object, the training images feature isolated object against dark background. The testing images depict the 20 different table-top scene with arrangement of random objects. As these scenes are well-suited for the task of this study, the testing images were considered for the use. The

complexity of these scenes ranges from a few isolated objects against clean dark background to multiple instances of objects with high clutter and occlusion against textured colored background as shown in Figure 5. From these scene images, five random scenes ranging between scene 10 to 20 were chosen for reconstruction of a different object in each scene. Also, the specific sensor images used in this study were images captured from Primesense sensor but only RGB images were used.

Figure 5: Overview of the T-LESS datasets illustrating; (a) different scenes present in the dataset, (b) individual objects used to comprise the scenes, (c) the 3D models provided by the datasets

Along with the training and testing images the dataset also provides the masks, specifically two types; one masking an entire object (full mask) and another including only the visible parts of the objects (visible mask), for the test scenes as in Figure 6. The availability of the masks makes the dataset more convenient to use. However, in case of other datasets where no masks are provided it should be possible to generate masks utilizing Segment Anything Model (SAM) (Kirillov et al., 2023) and SAM2 (Ravi et al., 2024). Furthermore, the T-LESS dataset also provides two types of 3D model of the objects; a manual CAD model and semi-automatically reconstructed model (Figure 5).

4.2 Implementation

The framework as shown in Figure 3 is based on 2DGS and utilizes an additional mask loss to segment object of interest from the scene. The model considers the sparse cloud points from SfM and the RGB input images as the inputs and optimizes the Gaussians as explained in section 3.2. The loss term coefficients value in Equation 12 are set to $\alpha = 100$ and $\beta = 0.05$ following 2DGS and $\delta = 0.01$ (Yang et al., 2024). All experiments in this study were performed with 30k iterations on a RTX 4090 GPU.

Figure 6: Types of mask provided in the T-LESS dataset: (a) example scene image, (b) full object mask, (c) visible object mask.

4.2.1 Mesh Extraction

In order to extract the meshes 2DGS mesh extraction approach is followed. Since, 2DGS reconstruct an entire scene the mesh extracted therefore will be for an entire scene. This meshes are then culled as post-processing steps to isolate the error metrics only for specific target objects. On the other hand, no post-processing of meshes are required when using our method as it already contains meshes of target object only.

4.3 Evaluations

The methods were evaluated for the quality of the reconstructed mesh and the novel view rendered. Further details on evaluation results and metrics are explained in section 4.3.1 and 4.3.2 .

4.3.1 Mesh Reconstruction

The quality of the reconstructed meshes were evaluated against the provided CAD model by T-LESS dataset. As explained in section 4.2.1, the reconstructed meshes from the 2DGS were culled to isolate the object and the meshes from our method already contains only the targeted object. For evaluation, a 3D point cloud processing software CloudCompare was used. The meshes were registered together with the CAD models and the average of distance between them were computed. The quantitative evaluation of quality can be found on Table 1.

Table 1: Quantitative results comparison of the mesh reconstruction quality between our method and 2DGS.

Scene ID	Obj ID	Signed Distance (mm) ours		Signed Distance (mm) 2dgs	
		Average	Std Dev	Average	Std Dev
10	23	0.551	2.416	0.654	1.383
11	10	0.859	1.352	0.775	1.395
14	20	0.391	2.389	0.418	1.556
16	12	0.354	1.04	0.323	1.038
17	4	-0.004	1.218	0.007	0.748

It can be observed that the quality of the reconstructed object from our method and the quality of the reconstruction from the 2DGS are close to each other with both models producing results with average distance less than 1mm. This is to be expected as our method doesn't make any changes to the regularization terms of 2DGS which are responsible for accurate geometry reconstruction. However, our method outperforms the 2DGS in optimization time significantly as shown in Table 2. The qualitative results of the reconstructed meshes are illustrated in Figure 7 and Figure 8.

Figure 7: Comparison of the reconstructed mesh quality from our method and 2DGS for object-id 23.

Figure 8: Comparison of the reconstructed mesh quality from our method and 2DGS for object-id 20.

4.3.2 Appearance Reconstruction

In this section, the quality of Novel View Rendering are evaluated and compared for the proposed method with 2DGS using peak signal-to-noise ratio (PSNR), structural similarity index (SSIM) and learned perceptual image patch similarity (LPIPS) as evaluation metrics. Since our method masks the object and the rendered view also consists of object only, the ground truth and rendered view of the 2DGS method were masked before the metrics computation for a fair evaluation. The metrics evaluated from 2DGS method for entire scene were also included to provide a comprehensive comparison on full scene and object focused evaluation.

The evaluation results are presented in Table 2 and Figure 9 and 10. The SSIM and LPIPS value for both our method and 2DGS method didn't show any significant disparity except for the case of 2DGS where entire scene was considered. On other hand, there is significant difference between the PSNR values between the two methods. While the PSNR for our method is certainly better than in the case of entire scene view from 2DGS, it was observed that the masked PSNR for 2DGS are significantly better than those of our method. The bad performance of our method is mainly due to the behavior of the model during the rendering of the views where the objects are occluded. This can be more clearly explained based on the visualization results from the Figure 11. It can be seen that in some cases of the occlusion, our model tends to render the actual components of the object to some extent which certainly differs from the ground truth. But in case of 2DGS both the ground truth and rendered view are masked which leads to the inclusion of the occlusion in rendered view as well. This disparity in the rendered view in case of occlusions yields in better PSNR values for 2DGS methods and lowers the PSNR values for our method.

Table 2: Comparison of methods based on training time, PSNR \uparrow , SSIM \uparrow , and LPIPS \downarrow . The metrics reported are average over the scenes.

Method	Training Time	PSNR \uparrow	SSIM	LPIPS
Ours (full_mask)	3:06	37.70	0.995	0.007
Ours (vis_mask)	3:02	35.07	0.994	0.009
2dgs (scene)	9:14	24.83	0.826	0.191
2dgs (full_mask)		45.79	0.997	0.004
2dgs (vis_mask)		47.19	0.998	0.003

(a) Scene -10

(b) Ground Truth

(c) Rendered View

Figure 9: Illustration of the rendered view from our method for different viewpoint in scene-10. The red box indicates the portion of object rendered which are occluded in ground truth scenario.

Figure 10: Illustration of the rendered view from our method for different viewpoint in scene-17. The red box indicates the portion of object rendered which are occluded in ground truth scenario.

Figure 11: Visual comparison between the ground truth and rendered views from 2DGS and our method. Each row shows: the input scene image, rendered view for the scene by 2DGS method, masked ground truth for 2DGS, masked rendered view for 2DGS followed by Ground truth and rendered view from our method. The red highlighted part are the occluded portion of object rendered in our method.

An additional evaluation was performed utilizing the visual mask in order to exclude the occlusion and compare the proposed method with our method (with vis_mask on Table 2). The metrics

for 2DGS were computed similarly as in previous case, by masking the ground truth and rendered images, using the visual mask for this instance. The evaluation results are again provided in Table 2 and Figure 12. However, the metrics were similar and showed once again that 2DGS has better PSNR values. In Figure 13, it can be seen that our method has tendency to render certain portion that should be occluded and hence not be present in rendered view. Our method, while having lower PSNR values than 2DGS object specific evaluation, still produces satisfactory results and is not significantly different in perceived quality, as measured by SSIM and LPIPS.

Figure 12: Illustration of the rendered view from our method (using visual masks) for different viewpoint in scene-11. The red box indicates the portion of object rendered which are occluded in ground truth scenario.

Figure 13: Visual comparison between the ground truth and rendered views from 2DGS and our method. The visual mask are used as masks in this case where mask is required. Each row shows: the input scene image, rendered view for the scene by 2DGS method, masked ground truth for 2DGS, masked rendered view for 2DGS followed by Ground truth and rendered view from our method. The red highlighted part are the occluded portion of object rendered in our method.

5 Discussion

This study explored the reconstruction of geometrically accurate object with 2DGS as baseline. It utilizes the mask loss with guidance from segmentation masks. The main objective of reconstruction of geometrically accurate object was achieved with significant efficiency over 2DGS. However, in case of the novel view rendering 2DGS performed better than our model. The rendered view from our method included the parts of object that were rendered although being occluded in reality. Further investigation of these aspects was beyond the scope of this study, mainly due to time limitation and need to keep the workload manageable within constraints of the lab rotation. Our method is also limited by the availability and quality of the mask as our mask loss depends on quality of the available mask. It also depends on the mask generation process and the performance may degrade significantly in case of systematic errors or unreliable masks.

6 Conclusion

In conclusion, this study successfully demonstrates a computationally efficient approach for object specific reconstruction using mask-guided loss and 2DGS serving as baseline. The proposed method acquired a sub-millimeter level accuracy in reconstruction while reducing the training time by almost one-third than original 2DGS approach indicating the suitability for an efficient object reconstruction task. Although, the method performed less effectively in novel view synthesis task - partially due to occlusion handling - it still produced reasonable results with the perceived quality in terms of SSIM and LPIPS. There are still possibility for future works build on this and enhance its performance while addressing the limitations.

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Appendices

A Additional Evaluation Tables and Figures

The following tables: Table 3, Table 4, Table 5, Table 6 and Table 7 provides the results of the evaluation of novel view rendering quality for each individual scenes in detail.

Table 3: Comparison of methods based on training time, PSNR \uparrow , SSIM \uparrow , and LPIPS \downarrow for test scene 10

Method	Avg Tr. Time	PSNR	SSIM	LPIPS
Ours (full_mask)	03:13	37.94	0.994	0.009
Ours (vis_mask)	03:02	34.41	0.992	0.012
2dgs (scene)	09:05	25.09	0.831	0.186
2dgs (full_mask)		45.48	0.996	0.005
2dgs (vis_mask)		46.37	0.997	0.004

Table 4: Comparison of methods based on training time, PSNR \uparrow , SSIM \uparrow , and LPIPS \downarrow for test scene 11

Method	Avg Tr. Time	PSNR	SSIM	LPIPS
Ours (full_mask)	03:05	38.88	0.996	0.005
Ours (vis_mask)	03:00	36.58	0.995	0.007
2dgs (scene)	09:30	24.64	0.831	0.187
2dgs (full_mask)		45.81	0.998	0.003
2dgs (vis_mask)		46.69	0.998	0.002

Table 5: Comparison of methods based on training time, PSNR \uparrow , SSIM \uparrow , and LPIPS \downarrow for test scene 14

Method	Avg Tr. Time	PSNR	SSIM	LPIPS
Ours (full_mask)	03:07	37.63	0.995	0.007
Ours (vis_mask)	03:05	34.91	0.994	0.010
2dgs (scene)	09:09	25.30	0.837	0.186
2dgs (full_mask)		46.33	0.997	0.004
2dgs (vis_mask)		47.48	0.998	0.003

Table 6: Comparison of methods based on training time, PSNR \uparrow , SSIM \uparrow , and LPIPS \downarrow for test scene 16

Method	Avg Tr. Time	PSNR	SSIM	LPIPS
Ours (full_mask)	03:04	37.93	0.994	0.006
Ours (vis_mask)	02:59	35.54	0.993	0.009
2dgs (scene)	09:24	23.57	0.806	0.207
2dgs (full_mask)		44.51	0.997	0.003
2dgs (vis_mask)		45.66	0.998	0.002

Table 7: Comparison of methods based on training time, PSNR \uparrow , SSIM \uparrow , and LPIPS \downarrow for test scene 17

Method	Avg Tr. Time	PSNR	SSIM	LPIPS \downarrow
Ours (full_mask)	03:02	37.37	0.995	0.006
Ours (vis_mask)	02:59	35.59	0.997	0.006
2dgs (scene)	09:23	23.62	0.820	0.188
2dgs (full_mask)		46.29	0.998	0.002
2dgs (vis_mask)		48.96	0.999	0.001

As previously stated, our model suffers in appearance reconstruction (NVS) task and as Figure 11, Figure 13 and Figure 14 illustrates the tendency of our model to render the occluded parts of object in some cases. However, the performance difference in terms of LPIPS and SSIM is marginal and the PSNR value, even though having a substantial gap, still falls within satisfactory range. It is worth noting that the rendered view of occluded object were not consistent and there were instances where the occluded object were rendered in alignment to ground truth as shown by Figure 15 . Due to the aforementioned constraints, the aspects contributing to such behavior of the proposed method were not pursued for this study.

Figure 14: Illustration of the examples where the occluded portion in rendered views are not conforming to the ground truth.

Figure 15: Illustration of the examples where the occluded portion in rendered views are in alignment to the ground truth.

In the Figure 16, Figure 17, Figure 18, Figure 19 and Figure 20 the qualitative results of the meshes reconstructed using our method and 2DGS method are presented. As mentioned in Section 4.3.1, the distance between the provided CAD model and the reconstructed mesh was computed in an open source 3D point processing software CloudCompare. The positive/negative signs indicate whether the points on the mesh are outside or inside respectively with respect to the surface of CAD model.

Figure 16: Comparison of reconstructed mesh visualizations and signed distance histograms between our method and the 2DGS approach for obj_id 23.

Figure 17: Comparison of reconstructed mesh visualizations and signed distance histograms between our method and the 2DGS approach for obj_id 10.

Figure 18: Comparison of reconstructed mesh visualizations and signed distance histograms between our method and the 2DGS approach for obj_id 20.

Figure 19: Comparison of reconstructed mesh visualizations and signed distance histograms between our method and the 2DGS approach for obj_id 12.

Figure 20: Comparison of reconstructed mesh visualizations and signed distance histograms between our method and the 2DGS approach for obj_id 04.